

Intellectual
Property
Office

Application

GB2613970.9

Application details

Application number	GB2613970.9
Application title	M.A.R.S. Companion: System and Method for Maintaining and Managing AI Companion Identity and Personality Persistence
Status	Filed

Dates

Lodged date	17 June 2026
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Applicants

Name	Address
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